

DESIGN FOR **OPEN** ACCESS IN THE **EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA** THROUGH **SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION (OPERAS-D)**

Deliverable 5.04 Report of Activities

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E-mail address	:	pierre.mounier@openedition.org
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Table of Contents

Communication activities	3
Introduction	3
Face-to-face communication	4
Website and blog	5
Social media	6
E-newsletter	7
News items and blog posts	7
OPERAS-D Final Conference	9
Dissemination activities	11
Design Study	11
The Visibility of Open Access Monographs in a European Context: Full Report	11
OPERAS-D deliverables	11
Promotional material	12
Visual identity	12
Toolbox	12
Flyer	13
Template for presentations	13
Stickers	13
Appendix	14
Programme of the OPERAS-D Final Conference	14
OPERAS Design Manual	14
OPERAS Flyer	14

1. Communication activities

Introduction

The OPERAS-D external communication strategy has aimed at promoting the project and the acknowledgement of its EU-funding to a large audience of stakeholders and target groups. The main target groups that were identified for OPERAS-D led to the following user stories:

Role <i>“as</i>	Need <i>they want to</i>	Intention <i>in order to ”</i>
Operators of e-infrastructure services	have a clear vision of their environment	define their development strategy
	know users’ needs	develop and provide effective services
Publishers	know current and future services provided by e-infrastructure services	align them with own services and workflows
	know the state-of-the-art of open access publishing technologies	stay competitive and in line with both the market and the users
	understand funders’ open access policies	provide proper access models for research outputs
	evaluate the sustainability of open access business models	include open access offerings in their business plans
Libraries	know current and future services provided by e-infrastructure services	reuse the services and enhance own infrastructures and service portfolios
	discover open access content pertinent for their patrons	enhance acquisition and increase provision of research literature
	understand the development of open access sector	to adapt their strategy
Universities (research and education communities)	know current and future services provided by e-infrastructure services and publishers	maximize the impact of their publications
	evaluate the cost of open access publications	plan funds and budgets

Therefore, for communicating the results of OPERAS-D and for developing advocacy material, the following target groups were of particular importance:

Primary target groups

- Non-commercial publishing institutions
- Research libraries

- Funding institutions, decision bodies
- European Commission (EC), national ministries

Secondary target groups

- Researchers
- Universities, scholarly societies, research and education communities

Face-to-face communication

An event calendar showing the most important upcoming conferences, exhibitions, expositions and workshops has been set up. The calendar has been created and made available for all project partners on Google Drive: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1RVsN4E-QDkQft16VeY9-DgOxW1AbKizK-fi4VpcsF38/edit>. Partners have been asked to indicate if they are planning on contributing to or attending an event in order to better coordinate the communication activities. Presentations were held by OPERAS-D partners at the following events:

Event	When	Where
DARIAH-EU Annual Event	26/27 April 2017	Berlin
Association of European University Presses (AEUP) Conference	17 May 2017	Stockholm
Digital Infrastructures for Research (DI4R) Conference	30 November – 1 December 2017	Brussels
2018 University Press Redux Conference	13/14 February 2018	London
Bulgarian Presidency Flagship Conference on Research Infrastructures	22/23 March 2018	Sofia
DARIAH-EU Annual Event	23/24 March 2018	Paris
Open Access in the Humanities	22 May 2018	Ljubljana
Digital History Workshop	14 June 2018	Athens
22nd International Conference on Electronic Publishing (ELPUB)	22-24 June 2018	Toronto

Website and blog

A project website has been set up and is available at www.operas-eu.org. The OPERAS project website is hosted by Hypotheses, a platform for humanities and social science research blogs that is run by OpenEdition. The website's content is maintained by the Max Weber Stiftung. The website's main feature is a blog, showing articles with news about the OPERAS research infrastructure. As of 19th June 2018, 35 articles have been posted.

The project websites' main pages are:

- "Home" – main page featuring an introduction to OPERAS (operas-eu.org)
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- "OPERAS-D" – page introducing OPERAS-D (operas-eu.org/operas-d)
- "HIRMEOS" – page introducing HIRMEOS (operas-eu.org/hirmeos)
- "Design Study" – html version and link to the full text pdf
- "Visibility of OA Monographs" – html version and link to the full text pdf
- "OPERAS Conference" – outlining the programme and results of the OPERAS-D Final Conference
- "Contact" – contact information and credits (operas-eu.org/contact)
- "Scientific Team" – information about the OPERAS scientific team
- "Promotional Material" – items for download, e.g. the logo (operas-eu.org/promotional-material)
- "Terms of Use" – detailing the terms of use

Other features on the website include:

- Quick links to all project partner
- Online surveys about services
- Quick links to the latest news ("newsdesk")
- A "follow" button to connect with OPERAS on Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn
- Registration for the newsletter
- Search function

The number of unique visitors of the OPERAS website has been steadily increasing and reached approx. 4.000 per month by the end of the project.

Figure 1: Unique visitors of the OPERAS website

Most visitors of the OPERAS website are located in the following countries: United States, France, Germany, Greece, Bulgaria, Singapore, Italy, European countries (not specified), United Kingdom.

Social media

OPERAS’ official Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook accounts have been registered under @OPERASEU. All social media accounts are maintained by the Max Weber Stiftung. The social media channels have reported the articles from the OPERAS blog, other news and events information for the social sciences and humanities (SSH) community, as well as information about OPERAS partners and the related Horizon2020 project HIRMEOS¹. Social media was also used for live reporting and participation in discussions during conferences, workshops and other events. As of 25th June 2018, Twitter has generated the largest impact with 685 tweets and 717 followers. Post impressions rank between 1,500 and 13,000 organic views. As seen in the statistics below (Twitter only allows to access the statistics of the last month of activities), profile visibility has been constantly increasing.

¹ see www.hirmeos.eu.

Figure 2: Twitter statistics

On LinkedIn, the personal page that was set up for OPERAS has 815 connections and typically appears in approx. 60 searches per week. The company page for OPERAS has reached a more tailored audience of 47 followers. The impact on Facebook with 50 followers was considerably smaller than that of the other social media channels.

E-newsletter

The newsletter was disseminated less frequently than originally planned. This was mainly due to the creation of the blog, which has taken over the function of a new sagent from the newsletter. Apart from the OPERAS mailing list, 73 people have subscribed to the newsletter. This number is expected to decrease however, as the new General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requires an active confirmation of the subscription and acceptance of the new terms of use.

News items and blog posts

The OPERAS-D project partners have actively promoted the project by publishing blog posts and news items in their respective languages to reach the SSH communities in their countries.

Max Weber Stiftung has communicated OPERAS-D through the following channels:

Blog “Digitale Redaktion”, an editorial about digital publishing.

- Blog post about the OPERAS-D final conference (in German), available at <https://editorial.hypotheses.org/190>

Max Weber Stiftung’s website

- Presenting OPERAS-D, available at www.maxweberstiftung.de/ueber-uns/virtuelle-infrastrukturen.html

Max Weber Stiftung's magazine "Weltweit vor Ort", which appears biannually

- OPERAS-D and OPERAS' activities were included in the magazine "Knowledge on the Move" - 02/2017 - and in "Science and Society" - 01/2018 - , available at <https://www.maxweberstiftung.de/en/newsfeed/magazine.html>

Sharing information about the activities of OPERAS-D, the Final Conference and the Design Study via **national mailing lists** for open access and the SSH:

- H/Soz/Kult - Communication and information service for historical research, available at <https://www.hsozkult.de/?language=en>
- InetBib - Internet in libraries, available at <http://www.inetbib.de/>
- DHd-Blog - digital humanities in German-speaking countries, available at <https://dhd-blog.org/>

EKT has communicated OPERAS-D through the following channels:

Open Access Blog <http://blog.openaccess.gr/>. The open access portal <http://www.openaccess.gr/> and blog are the key portals for communicating open science/open access issues of interest to the Greek scientific community and the general public.

- Post presenting OPERAS-D (in Greek), available at <http://blog.openaccess.gr/?p=4271>
- Post on the Landscape Study (in Greek) available at <http://blog.openaccess.gr/?p=4313>

EKT website <http://www.ekt.gr/el>

- Presenting OPERAS-D project (in Greek) available at <http://www.ekt.gr/el/news/20604>
- Presenting the final conference (in Greek) available at <http://www.ekt.gr/el/news/21669>

and also available in English at <http://www.ekt.gr/en/news/21715>

Innovation Magazine Published 3 times a year (5.000 recipients/issue-printed version). "Innovation" is available both in printed and online.

OPERAS-D was presented in issue 106 (December 2016-February 2017) <http://kainotomia.ekt.gr/issue/2017/106/files/assets/basic-html/index.html#2>

The OPERAS-D landscape study was featured in issue 108 (June-August 2017) <http://kainotomia.ekt.gr/issue/2017/108/files/assets/basic-html/index.html#2>

eNewsletter. EKT's eNewsletter (in Greek) is published twice a month and has a reach of 30.000. The final conference has been advertised through the eNewsletter

OPERAS-D Final Conference

The OPERAS-D Final Conference was organized by the National Documentation Centre (EKT) from 31 May – 1 June 2018 in Athens. The OPERAS-D budget had allowed for the invitation of several speakers, including

- Lars Bjørnshauge (DOAJ)
- Matthew Dovey (Head of e-Infrastructure Strategy, Jisc; EGI)
- Jacques Lafait (University of Jussieu, Jussieu Call)
- Damien Lecarpentier (EUDAT) John Willinsky (Director of the Public Knowledge Project)
- Sven Fund (Knowledge Unlatched)
- Delfim Leao (Coimbra University)
- Jadranka Stojanovski (Hrcak)
- Suzanne Dumouchel (Huma Num)
- John Willinsky (PKP)
- Abel Packer (Sciel)
- Dirk Pieper (University of Bielefeld, OA2020 Initiative)
- Laurent Romary (DARIAH)
- Thomas Stäcker (Director of Darmstadt University Library)

In addition, the budget allowed us to cover travel and accommodation costs of the following participants, members of OPERAS

- Andrea Bertino (Georg-August-University Göttingen)
- Aysa Ekanger (UIT The Arctic University)
- Klaudia Grabowska (IBL PAN)
- Gregor Horstkemper (Bavarian State Library)
- Barbara Jedrasko (IBL PAN)
- Patricia Kern (German Historical Institute Rome - Max Weber Stiftung)

The conference was actively advertised by all project partners as well as all OPERAS members in their national SSH communities. Moreover, the conference was announced via the following means:

- **OpenAIRE:** The Final Conference was advertised in the events section of OpenAIRE <https://www.openaire.eu/events/eventdetail/547/-/operas-conference-open-scholarly-communication-in-europe-addressing-the-coordination-challenge>.
- **OASPA:** The Final Conference was advertised in the events section.
- **ENRESSH:** The final conference was advertised via the ENRESSH mailing list
- **LIBER:** The final conference was advertised via the LIBER mailing list

- **HIRMEOS:** The final conference was advertised on the project’s website, newsletter and social media accounts
- **EKT eNewsletter:** The final conference has been advertised through the eNewsletter (various issues)
- **Max Weber Stiftung’s magazine “Weltweit vor Ort”** and the foundation’s **social media** accounts.

285 people had pre-registered for the conference. In addition to the speakers, 73 people attended the event, while around 20 watched it through live streaming (available at www.ekt.gr/el/events/program/21642). The conference was also actively discussed on Twitter using the hashtag #OPERASconf. Speakers, participants and live stream watchers reacted to the topics discussed during the conference.

The conference’s programme is available in Appendix I. A visual identity for the Final Conference was developed by EKT.

Visual Identity of the OPERAS-D Final Conference

2. Dissemination activities

Design Study

The OPERAS Design Study is the outcome of the OPERAS-D project. The main part of the OPERAS Design Study comprises four studies that explore the landscape of OPERAS' field of activity, establish the technical mapping of the OPERAS consortium, present a survey on users' needs concerning scientific communication and academic publishing, and finally foresee the development of the governance scheme and business model of the future infrastructure within the ESFRI framework. The studies' main finding is the fragmentation of OPERAS field of work. Thus, OPERAS vision and mission is integration. The study can be found on the project website (operas-eu.org/design-study) as well as under the following doi: [10.5281/zenodo.1009544](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1009544).

The Visibility of Open Access Monographs in a European Context: Full Report

OPERAS-D project partner KU Research, in cooperation with OPERAS, has launched a report on the visibility of Open Access monographs in a European context. This report explores the extent to which Open Access specialist scholarly books can be seen by the communities that might make use of them. It also identifies the key challenges that will need to be tackled in order to ensure that Open Access books are fully integrated into digital landscapes of scholarship; as well as the steps that need to be taken to achieve this goal. The report focuses on Open Access books made available by publishers and platforms that are part of the OPERAS research infrastructure. Specialist scholarly books are the core research output of the Humanities and Social Sciences. Ensuring that they are integrated into digital landscapes of scholarship will play a decisive role in the future of these disciplines, and their impact on the world. Identifying gaps in existing infrastructure and creating a roadmap to address them is vital groundwork. The full report is available at the project website (www.operas-eu.org/visibility-oa-monographs) as well as under the following doi: [10.5281/zenodo.1230342](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1230342).

OPERAS-D deliverables

All OPERAS-D deliverables that were marked in the grant agreement as “public” have been uploaded to the OPERAS website at www.operas-eu.org/projects/operas-d and/or given a doi and deposited in Zenodo in the respective OPERAS community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/operaseu/?page=1&size=20>.

3. Promotional material

Visual identity

A visual identity for OPERAS and the project OPERAS-D has been prepared by the design agency “Oktober Kommunikationsdesign” (<http://oktober.de>). The OPERAS Design Manual is available in Appendix II. All items of the visual identity for OPERAS have been uploaded to the OPERAS website (“promotional material”) and the toolbox and include the following:

A logo displaying the project acronym “OPERAS” in different formats (eps, jpg web and print format, pdf, png, svg)

OPERAS

open access in the european research area through scholarly communication

An extension of the logo displaying the acronym “OPERAS-D”

OPERAS-D

A web banner (png and jpg)

A color scheme defining two primary and 2 secondary colors

primary colour “red”: 170/10/45, #AA0A2D
 primary colour “purple”: 105/35/100, #692364
 secondary colour “black”: 0/0/0, #000000
 secondary colour “grey”: 135/135/135, #878787

A flyer, 6 pages, DIN long format

The flyer is currently being developed and soon to be made available. The content of the flyer can be adapted as the project evolves.

Typography

The two fonts used for most communication and dissemination activities are the serif font Utopia Std and the sans serif font Univers LT Pro.

Toolbox

A toolbox including communication and dissemination material that can be downloaded by interested partners has been prepared. The material is available on Google Drive: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/OB1KFzkQSBifyZGlfazBHLUJ6cke>. The most relevant

items for communication and dissemination activities of project partners are also available for download on the OPERAS website: <http://operas-eu.org/promotional-material>.

Flyer

A flyer has been created and was regularly updated. The OPERAS-D project budget has allowed for the printing of 1.000 copies which have been disseminated at various events. In addition, EKT printed 300 copies for dissemination during the final conference. The latest version of the flyer is in Appendix III.

Template for presentations

A basic template for presentations (Power Point) has been developed and is available (pptx) in the toolbox.

Stickers

3.000 OPERAS stickers have been printed and were disseminated at various events.

4. Appendix

Programme of the OPERAS-D Final Conference

OPERAS Design Manual

OPERAS Flyer

Table of Contents

Communication activities	3
Introduction	3
Face-to-face communication	4
Website and blog	5
Social media	5
E-newsletter	6
News items and blog posts	6
OPERAS-D Final Conference	7
Dissemination activities	10
Design Study	10
The Visibility of Open Access Monographs in a European Context: Full Report	10
OPERAS-D deliverables	10
Promotional material	11
Visual identity	11
Toolbox	11
Flyer	12
Template for presentations	12
Stickers	12
Appendix	13
Programme of the OPERAS-D Final Conference	13
OPERAS Design Manual	13
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eNewsletter. EKT’s eNewsletter (in Greek) is published twice a month and has a reach of 30.000. The final conference has been advertised through the eNewsletter

OPERAS-D Final Conference

The OPERAS-D Final Conference was organized by the National Documentation Centre (EKT) from 31 May – 1 June 2018 in Athens. The OPERAS-D budget had allowed for the invitation of several speakers, including

- Lars Bjørnshauge (DOAJ)
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- Abel Packer (Sciel)
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- Laurent Romary (DARIAH)
- Thomas Stäcker (Director of Darmstadt University Library)

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The conference was actively advertised by all project partners as well as all OPERAS members in their national SSH communities. Moreover, the conference was announced via the following means:

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- **OASPA:** The Final Conference was advertised in the events section.
- **ENRESSH:** The final conference was advertised via the ENRESSH mailing list
- **LIBER:** The final conference was advertised via the LIBER mailing list
- **HIRMEOS:** The final conference was advertised on the project's website, newsletter and social media accounts
- **EKT eNewsletter:** The final conference has been advertised through the eNewsletter (various issues)
- **Max Weber Stiftung's magazine "Weltweit vor Ort"** and the foundation's **social media** accounts.

285 people had pre-registered for the conference. In addition to the speakers, 73 people attended the event, while around 20 watched it through live streaming (available at www.ekt.gr/el/events/program/21642). The conference was also actively discussed on Twitter using the hashtag #OPERASconf. Speakers, participants and live stream watchers reacted to the topics discussed during the conference.

The conference's programme is available in Appendix I. A visual identity for the Final Conference was developed by EKT.

Visual Identity of the OPERAS-D Final Conference

2. Dissemination activities

Design Study

The OPERAS Design Study is the outcome of the OPERAS-D project. The main part of the OPERAS Design Study comprises four studies that explore the landscape of OPERAS' field of activity, establish the technical mapping of the OPERAS consortium, present a survey on users' needs concerning scientific communication and academic publishing, and finally foresee the development of the governance scheme and business model of the future infrastructure within the ESFRI framework. The studies' main finding is the fragmentation of OPERAS field of work. Thus, OPERAS vision and mission is integration. The study can be found on the project website (operas-eu.org/design-study) as well as under the following doi: [10.5281/zenodo.1009544](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1009544).

The Visibility of Open Access Monographs in a European Context: Full Report

OPERAS-D project partner KU Research, in cooperation with OPERAS, has launched a report on the visibility of Open Access monographs in a European context. This report explores the extent to which Open Access specialist scholarly books can be seen by the communities that might make use of them. It also identifies the key challenges that will need to be tackled in order to ensure that Open Access books are fully integrated into digital landscapes of scholarship; as well as the steps that need to be taken to achieve this goal. The report focuses on Open Access books made available by publishers and platforms that are part of the OPERAS research infrastructure. Specialist scholarly books are the core research output of the Humanities and Social Sciences. Ensuring that they are integrated into digital landscapes of scholarship will play a decisive role in the future of these disciplines, and their impact on the world. Identifying gaps in existing infrastructure and creating a roadmap to address them is vital groundwork. The full report is available at the project website (www.operas-eu.org/visibility-oa-monographs) as well as under the following doi: [10.5281/zenodo.1230342](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1230342).

OPERAS-D deliverables

All OPERAS-D deliverables that were marked in the grant agreement as “public” have been uploaded to the OPERAS website at www.operas-eu.org/projects/operas-d and/or given a doi and deposited in Zenodo in the respective OPERAS community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/operaseu/?page=1&size=20>.

3. Promotional material

Visual identity

A visual identity for OPERAS and the project OPERAS-D has been prepared by the design agency “Oktober Kommunikationsdesign” (<http://oktober.de>). The OPERAS Design Manual is available in Appendix II. All items of the visual identity for OPERAS have been uploaded to the OPERAS website (“promotional material”) and the toolbox and include the following:

A logo displaying the project acronym “OPERAS” in different formats (eps, jpg web and print format, pdf, png, svg)

open access in the european research area through scholarly communication

An extension of the logo displaying the acronym “OPERAS-D”

A web banner (png and jpg)

A color scheme defining two primary and 2 secondary colors

primary colour “red”: 170/10/45, #AA0A2D
 primary colour “purple”: 105/35/100, #692364
 secondary colour “black”: 0/0/0, #000000
 secondary colour “grey”: 135/135/135, #878787

A flyer, 6 pages, DIN long format

The flyer is currently being developed and soon to be made available. The content of the flyer can be adapted as the project evolves.

Typography

The two fonts used for most communication and dissemination activities are the serif font Utopia Std and the sans serif font Univers LT Pro.

Toolbox

A toolbox including communication and dissemination material that can be downloaded by interested partners has been prepared. The material is available on Google Drive: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/OB1KFzkQSBifyZGlfazBHLUJ6cke>. The most relevant

items for communication and dissemination activities of project partners are also available for download on the OPERAS website: <http://operas-eu.org/promotional-material>.

Flyer

A flyer has been created and was regularly updated. The OPERAS-D project budget has allowed for the printing of 1.000 copies which have been disseminated at various events. In addition, EKT printed 300 copies for dissemination during the final conference. The latest version of the flyer is in Appendix III.

Template for presentations

A basic template for presentations (Power Point) has been developed and is available (pptx) in the toolbox.

Stickers

3.000 OPERAS stickers have been printed and were disseminated at various events.

4. Appendix

Programme of the OPERAS-D Final Conference

OPERAS Design Manual

OPERAS Flyer

31 May -
1 June 2018
ATHENS

Open Scholarly Communication in Europe: Addressing the Coordination Challenge

National Hellenic Research Foundation
48 Vas. Konstantinou Av., GR-11635, Athens

May 31st 2018

09.00-9.30 **Registration**

9.30-10.00 **Welcome**

Evi Sachini, Director of National Documentation Centre, EKT

Pierre Mounier, Coordinator of OPERAS, Deputy Director of OpenEdition

10.00-10.30 **Keynote: Open Science in Europe**

Victoria Tsoukala, Policy Officer, Unit Open Data Policies and Science Cloud, European Commission

10.30-11.00 **Designing an Infrastructure for Open Scholarly Communication:
Operas-D Findings**

Pierre Mounier, Coordinator of OPERAS, Deputy Director of OpenEdition

11.00-11.30 **Coffee Break**

11.30-13.00 **Scholarly E-Infrastructures Across Europe. Models of Coordination**

MODERATOR: Matthew Dovey, Head of e-Infrastructure Strategy, Jisc

Coordination through the market:

Elco Ferwerda (OAPEN), **Graham Stone** (Jisc)

Coordination through government: Pierre Mounier (OpenEdition),

Michael Kaiser (MWS), **Maciej Maryl** (IBL PAN), **Marina Angelaki** (EKT),

Coordination through community: Elena Giglia (University of Turin),

Delfim Leao (Coimbra University), **Jadranka Stojanovski** (University of Zadar)

13.00-14.00 **Lunch**

14.00-15.30 **Poster Session: What is at stake?**

Presentation of OPERAS working groups' White Papers

15.30-16.00 **Coffee Break**

16.00-17.00 Funding Opportunities to Support Open Scholarly Communication

MODERATOR:

Daša Radovič, International Cooperation Manager at OpenEdition

Victoria Tsoukala, European Commission

Lars Bjørnshauge, DOAJ

Suzanne Dumouchel, Huma-Num

17.00-17.30 **KEYNOTE:** A View from America (Canada)
John Willinsky, Director of the Public Knowledge Project

June 1st 2018

09.00-9.30 Registration

9.30-10.00 **Keynote:** A View from America (Brazil)
Abel Packer, Director of SciELO

10.00-11.30 EOSC. The Vertical Coordination Challenge
MODERATOR: **Suzanne Dumouchel**, Huma-Num and DARIAH Program Implementation Officer
Damien Lecarpentier, EUDAT
Laurent Romary, DARIAH
Matthew Dovey, EGI
Natalia Manola, OpenAIRE

11.30-12.00 Coffee Break

12.00-13.00 Flipping Journals or Changing the System? The Need for Coordination
MODERATOR: **Thomas Stäcker**, Director of the Darmstadt University Library
Jacques Lafait, University of Jussieu, Jussieu Call
Dirk Pieper, University of Bielefeld, OA2020 Initiative
Saskia de Vries, Fair Open Access Alliance Project Leader

13.00-13.45 Conclusions & next Conference

13.45-15.00 Lunch

15.00-17.00 **OPERAS partners meeting** (by invitation only) EKT Media Room

logo with subline

OPERAS

open access in the european research
area through scholarly communication

OPERAS

open access in the european research
area through scholarly communication

subline minimal 6pt

symbol

Wordmark and Logo

The OPERAS logo consists of a symbol and a wordmark, which are used as a unit. The symbol consists of the opened capital letter "O" and is accentuated by a bracket, symbolizing the network/governing body.

The letters are based on the font Utopia Std. The "open" letters symbolize the theme of "openness". The OPERAS logo, depending on the use and size, can be used with or without subline. The subline should not be smaller than 6pt.

The logo can furthermore be used separately, e.g. as favicon.

Wordmark and Logo

The OPERAS logo can be used either with or without subline.

There is a version of the logo that is completed by the ending-D (representing Design).

The proportions and spacing, as well as the colour values of the logo and wordmark are not to be changed.

Red

Colour (printing)
CMYK 7/100/70/30
Colour (web)
sRGB 170/10/45

Purple

Colour (printing)
CMYK 50/90/0/40
Colour (web)
sRGB 105/35/100

OPERAS Colours

The brand colours are red and purple. These colours are complemented by a pure black, which is used for the subline. A grey colour is used in the black-and-white version of the logo.

Black

Colour (printing)
CMYK 0/0/0/100
Colour (web)
sRGB 0/0/0

Grey

Colour (printing)
CMYK 0/0/0/60
Colour (web)
sRGB 135/135/135

Utopia Std

Display
Regular
Sembibold

Univers LT Pro

Light
Roman
Bold

Corporate Typeface

The serif font Utopia Std and the sans serif font Univers LT Pro are combined for the corporate design. The wordmark is set in a modified semibold Utopia Std. The subline uses a light version of Univers.

Utopia Std Semibold

abcdefghijklmnopqrstvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMN**OP**QRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789 &%,.!?,“/

Univers LT Pro Light

abcdefghijklmnopqrstvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMN**OP**QRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789 &%,.!?,“/

Open scholarly communication in Europe

OPERAS – distributed Research Infrastructure

Contact us

Pierre.Mounier@openedition.org

Follow us on:
Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter
@OPERASEU and @HIRMEOS

Subscribe to the OPERAS newsletter at:
www.operas-eu.org and to the HIRMEOS
newsletter at www.hirmeos.eu

Main goal: to coordinate and pool university-led scholarly communication activities in Europe, particularly in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), in view of enabling Open Science as the standard practice.

Outcome: more efficient, fair, inclusive and sustainable scholarly communication ecosystem for European researchers.

OPERAS coordinates services, practices and technology across main actors in the SSH scholarly communication in Europe

- to provide joint services;
- to mutualize activities of strategic scholarly communication actors and stakeholders (research institutions, libraries, platforms, publishers, funders) in their transition to open science;
- to develop common good practice standards for digital open access publishing, infrastructures, services, editorial qualities, business models and funding streams;
- to explore alternative measurements of impact in the SSH;
- and to offer sustained training along common standards to researchers and other stakeholders on all of the above.

OPERAS final aim is

- to clarify the landscape of open access books for libraries and funders through a single certification service based on DOAB;
- to improve the accessibility and dissemination of research output in the SSH through a single discovery service based on Isidore;
- and to increase the impact of multidisciplinary research on societal challenges through a single research for society service based on Hypotheses.

OPERAS Services are deployed at 3 levels following the principle of subsidiarity

1. Upgrade existing publishing services through

- a. Communication and advocacy for open science
- b. Training for publishers and researchers
- c. Research & Development to provide innovative tools
- d. Development of sustainable and fair business models for open access

2. Integrate to the European Open Science Cloud through

- a. Standardization of technologies and information systems
- b. Adoption of scientific and editorial best practices
- c. Interoperability with other infrastructures at different levels

3. Offer unified services in the European Research Area

- a. OPERAS Certification Service (DOAB)
- b. OPERAS Discovery Service (Isidore)
- c. OPERAS Research for Society Service (Hypotheses)

OPERAS gathers 37 organizations from 15 countries and is led by a 9 member core group.

OPERAS is coordinated from France by OpenEdition and Huma-Num.

OPERAS-D supports the 9 main partners (core group) of the OPERAS network in the development of a European e-infrastructure for open access publications in the SSH.

The project addresses long-term requirements for the development of the e-infrastructure and community building, as well as seeks to expand other interested parties within and beyond Europe, and in diverse fields of the SSH.

As a key objective, the OPERAS-D project has prepared a design study that defines governance models, scientific and technical concepts for future services that the infrastructure will provide, and has established a roadmap to achieve these goals according to the requirements for long term sustainability.

OPERAS-D engages the current and future partners in the OPERAS network to strengthen the community and develop the network of partners participating in OPERAS across Europe, specifically in central European countries.

Partners: Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS)/CLEO, KU Research, Max Weber Stiftung (MWS), National Documentation Centre (EKT)/NHRF, OAPEN

Duration: 18 months from January 2017

www.operas-eu.org/operas-d

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No731031

HIRMEOS (High Integration of Research Monographs in the European open science infrastructure) focuses on the monograph as a significant mode of scholarly communication in the SSH and tackles the main obstacles of the full integration of publishing platforms supporting open access monographs.

The project improves 5 open access books publishing platforms (OpenEdition Books, OAPEN Library, EKT Open Book Press, Ubiquity Press, Göttingen University Press), enhancing their technical capacities and services, rendering technologies and content interoperable and embedding them fully into the European Open Science Cloud.

HIRMEOS prototypes innovative services by providing additional data, links and interactions to the documents, paving the way to new potential tools for research assessment, which is still a major challenge in the SSH. The platforms participating are enriched with tools that enable identification, authentication and interoperability, and tools that enrich information and entity extraction, the ability to annotate monographs, and gather usage and alternative metric data. HIRMEOS also enriches the technical capacities of the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB), a most significant indexing service for open access monographs globally, to receive automated information for ingestion, while it also develops a structured certification system to document monograph peer-review.

Partners: Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS)/CLEO, DARIAH ERIC, Georg-August-University Göttingen (UGOE), Max Weber Stiftung (MWS), National Documentation Centre (EKT)/NHRF, OAPEN, Open Books Publishers, Ubiquity Press, University of Turin (UniTo)

Duration: 30 months from January 2017

www.hirmeos.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No731102

